

Modelling the Future of Airport Accessibility: A Synthetic Population and Discrete Choice Model Approach to UAM and CCAM Demand at Brussels Airport

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Author contributions

Behzad Bamdad Mehrabani: Conceptualization; Methodology; Software; Formal analysis; Validation; Writing – original draft; Visualization. Vincent Henrion: Methodology; Writing – review & editing. Sebastian Hörl: Conceptualization; Software; Validation; Writing – review & editing. Nikola Ivanov: Writing – review & editing; Investigation. Bojana Mirkovic: Writing – review & editing; Investigation. Juan Blasco: Project administration; Writing – review & editing. Elke Bossaert: Data curation.

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Abstract

The emergence of Urban Air Mobility (UAM) and Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) offers transformative potential for airport accessibility, promising faster and more personalised connections to major air hubs. However, accurately forecasting the demand for these future transport modes remains a key challenge due to their limited real-world presence and reliance on speculative user preferences. This paper presents a robust and flexible methodology for assessing the future modal split of airport access, integrating both current and emerging mobility options within a discrete choice modelling (DCM) framework. Using a nested logit model calibrated on survey data from over 29,000 Belgian passengers at Brussels Airport, we developed a general-coefficient-based utility specification that enables the integration of hypothetical modes such as UAM and CCAM. This model was then applied to a synthetic population of airport passengers generated via iterative proportional fitting and spatial enrichment. By incorporating realistic operational assumptions for UAM and CCAM, we estimated demand under future scenarios. The results indicate that UAM and CCAM could capture 4.7% and 6.8% of airport access trips respectively, with modal shifts primarily originating from taxi and private car users. This demand modelling framework is assumption-agnostic and adaptable, providing a versatile tool for policy analysis and infrastructure planning as these technologies approach deployment. Future applications will benefit from updated data as these services are piloted, supporting more precise and policy-relevant demand estimations.

Keyword: Airport accessibility; urban air mobility; connected and automated vehicles; mode choice modelling; synthetic population; airport ground access; travel demand forecasting

1. Introduction

Airport accessibility – the ease and efficiency with which travellers reach an airport – is a critical aspect of airport planning and regional mobility. Effective landside access influences an airport’s catchment area, modal share, and even its environmental footprint [1]. Traditionally, ground access planning has focused on road and public transport improvements, but the last decade has seen a surge of interest in emerging transport modes that could transform airport access. In particular, Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM), exemplified by connected and self-driving vehicles, and Urban Air Mobility (UAM), on-demand short-range flights by the electric vertical take-off and landing (eVTOL) colloquially referred to as “air taxi” service, are envisaged as game-changers. These innovations promise faster, more convenient trips that bypass road congestion, but also pose new challenges for integration, infrastructure, and policy.

This study addresses the challenge of forecasting demand for these novel transport modes, which is difficult due to the absence of revealed preference (RP) data and the limitations of stated preference (SP) surveys. To overcome this, we develop a discrete choice model (DCM) that integrates both existing and emerging modes of airport access. The model uses general behavioural coefficients derived from real-world data on current modes to simulate demand for UAM and CCAM. Applied to a synthetic population of Brussels Airport passengers, the framework allows us to estimate future modal splits under realistic operational scenarios. In doing so, the study contributes a robust and flexible methodology that supports both short-term scenario analysis and long-term planning as empirical data on these technologies becomes available.

The research questions guiding this work are therefore threefold: (i) how can we model demand for UAM and CCAM in airport access despite the absence of operational data, (ii) what is the likely modal

share of these services compared to existing modes, and (iii) which traveller segments are most likely to adopt them? By answering these questions, we provide evidence-based insights for policymakers, airport operators, and mobility service providers preparing for the deployment of CCAM and UAM. To situate these research questions within the broader scientific context, it is essential to review the growing body of studies that have explored how CCAM and UAM may reshape airport access and disrupt existing mobility patterns.

2. Literature Review

Recent studies have begun modelling how CCAM and UAM might improve or disrupt airport access. Ride-sourcing services (e.g., Uber) have already demonstrated how new mobility options can significantly alter airport ground transport demand [2]. CCAM (e.g., shared autonomous vehicles) could further increase convenience but might undermine established revenue models like parking [3]. Likewise, UAM services could sharply cut travel times to airports, albeit likely at premium cost [4]. Given the rapid developments in autonomous driving and aerial mobility technology, there is a pressing need to understand their potential real-world impacts on airport accessibility.

Studies on UAM in an airport access context converge on the idea that UAM airport shuttle service could greatly reduce travel times to airports, albeit initially serving a niche market of high-paying, time-sensitive travellers. A clear benefit of UAM is the ability to bypass ground congestion. In a comprehensive modelling study for UAM airport shuttle system in Beijing, Lv *et al.* found that a well-designed UAM network could cut door-to-door travel times by nearly 30% compared to existing modes [4]. Their optimized design proved operationally robust: the UAM shuttle system was able to accommodate 95% of pre-booked trips and over 90% of on-demand (ad hoc) trip requests, indicating potential for high reliability and service quality in nominal conditions.

Boddupalli *et al.* explore potential commuter demand for eVTOL ride services in five large US metropolitan areas by means of a stated-choice survey and mixed-logit modelling [5]. Their 2,383 full-time workers (income \geq USD 100k) each evaluated eight hypothetical trips comparing their current mode with an air-taxi alternative. They find that about 14 % of respondents always choose the air taxi and 14 % never choose it, implying a polarised market with a sizeable segment who will not consider the mode at launch.

Brunelli, Ditta and Postorino fuse revealed- and stated-preference evidence from 197 Italian passengers to model prospective demand for eVTOL airport shuttles, calibrating three multinomial and a mixed logit with log-normal time and cost coefficients that expose substantial taste heterogeneity [6]. Fares emerge as the chief driver (mean values span 28–42 €/h) while adoption propensity rises with income, business-trip purpose and frequent flying; younger adults prize low-cost shared rides, whereas older travellers value privacy and will pay for solo flights. The authors temper stated-preference bias through simplified choice tasks, descriptive fact-sheets and mixed on-line/airport recruitment, yet concede that optimistic 2030–35 vertiport assumptions and a youth-skewed sample may inflate demand estimates and curb external validity.

Market adoption of UAM is expected to be concentrated among certain traveller segments. Across multiple studies, the profile of likely early UAM users is quite consistent: affluent, frequent flyers who place a premium on time savings. Jang *et al.* confirmed that people with higher incomes and those already inclined to pay for speed (e.g., frequent taxi users who like to arrive early for flights) are far more likely to choose a UAM airport shuttle over cheaper options [7]. Over 2,600 respondents chose preferred modes in various scenarios with different travel times, costs, and transfer requirements. The majority of respondents preferred the airport bus (49%) and train (24%) for airport access, with fewer

choosing private cars (16%), taxis (6%), or UAM (4%). These demographic tendencies suggest UAM initial demand will skew towards business travellers and affluent leisure travellers seeking to save time. Also, the study of Samadzad et al. revealed that that UAM for weekly business trips represents the most demanding market segment [8].

Because of this, the mode share of UAM is projected to be modest in the near term, but non-negligible in certain contexts. For instance, a study by Rimjha *et al.* for Dallas-Fort Worth estimated that, with a dense network of about 50 vertiports, UAM might capture up to 4% of airport trips in that region [9]. However, Rimjha et al. use optimistic pricing at around \$2 per mile, which is on the lower end of spectrum [10], and note that UAM could have “considerable potential” if per-mile costs can be kept below about \$4, beyond which demand dropped off.

Overall, the literature’s key message on UAM is one of optimistic potential tempered by practical realities [11]. UAM can greatly improve airport accessibility for cities suffering road congestion – the technology can work and deliver tangible benefits in travel time and service quality. However, early services will target a niche market and face hurdles in cost, capacity and airspace integration. Many studies underscore that substantial infrastructure investment (vertiports, air traffic management integration) and regulatory support will be needed to make UAM a safe and reliable option for airport access [12]. Pilot projects and partnerships are already underway, for instance, several airlines and UAM startups have announced airport shuttle trials in the mid-2020s [13], [14], [15], [16], and these will provide valuable real-world data beyond the models.

On the other hand, automated vehicles and shared mobility services are expected to profoundly affect airport ground access. A consistent finding is that autonomous vehicles (AVs) could offer travellers greater convenience but at the same time threaten traditional airport revenue streams and require new management strategies. Wang & Zhang estimated that the widespread use of AVs would significantly change how passengers access airports like Tampa International Airport (TPA) and San Francisco International Airport (SFO) [3]. In their simulation, many passengers in an AV-friendly future would avoid parking at the airport or using conventional taxis/rental cars, instead arriving via autonomous drop-off. Gurusurthy & Kockelman found a similar trend in their Austin Bergstrom case study: a fleet of shared autonomous vehicles (SAVs) with aggressive ride-pooling could reduce total vehicle trips to the airport by up to 30% but also slash airport access fee revenues by ~46% under current fee structures [2]. Fu *et al.* conducted an SP questionnaire in the Munich region to study mode choice between private car, public transport, an autonomous taxi, and an autonomous flying taxi (UAM) [17]. Among the evaluated service attributes, total travel time emerged as the most influential factor in determining users’ mode choice. Cost followed closely behind as a key determinant. Interestingly, walking and waiting time was not statistically significant for the autonomous modes, suggesting that users might perceive waiting for Autonomous Taxi (AT) or autonomous flying taxis (AFT) services differently from waiting for public transport. Safety played a critical role: when AFT and AT were perceived as less safe than driving, their overall utility declined markedly. Notably, the value of time associated with AFT was the highest among all modes, indicating that respondents were willing to pay a substantial premium for faster travel using flying taxis.

Another important finding is that CCAM could expand the effective catchment area of airports, altering travel patterns on a regional scale. Karam *et al.* project that autonomous driving may enable more travellers to bypass their local airports in favour of distant hub airports that offer better flight options [18]. In other words, a passenger living in a smaller city might be willing to endure a much longer drive in a comfortable self-driving car to use a major airport (a phenomenon known as *airport leakage*). Their model, applied to the Charlotte and Atlanta metro regions, suggests that as AV adoption rises,

leakage to large hubs could increase, which would lead to extra long-distance car travel and potentially shift demand away from regional airports.

From an operational perspective, CCAM is expected to improve ground access efficiency and passenger experience. Connected vehicle technology can enable smarter traffic management on airport roads. For instance, vehicles communicating with traffic signals and each other could reduce delays on approach roads. Mahesh & Calvert in a sustainability review observe that autonomous electric shuttle buses could play a role in decarbonising airport access in the future [1] – for example by connecting transit hubs to terminals with zero-emission AVs, thus encouraging travellers to use public transport for most of the journey. In summary, CCAM-based solutions offer convenience and potential environmental benefits (when electrified), but careful planning is required to handle financial impacts, infrastructure needs, and regional demand shifts.

A key methodological gap in the current literature on accessibility to airport using new modes of transport is the heavy reliance on SP data to estimate demand for UAM and CCAM. Because these services are not yet widely operational, researchers often must ask people how they *might* use UAM or autonomous shuttles in hypothetical scenarios. Many demand studies to date have thus been built on SP surveys or stated-choice experiments [19]. For example, Coppola *et al.* combined revealed-preference data on current travel with an extensive SP survey of attitudes toward UAM to calibrate their mode choice model for Milan [20]. While SP-based analyses are invaluable for gauging initial interest, they have well-known drawbacks. Respondents’ stated intentions may not translate into real-world behaviour due to optimism bias, unfamiliarity with the new mode, or the inability to accurately imagine service quality. In the case of UAM and CCAM, travellers have little to no practical experience with air taxis or self-driving shuttles, so their preferences are speculative. Consequently, models built solely on SP data risk misestimating demand – for instance, overestimating adoption if respondents are overly enthusiastic *or* underestimating it if they remain sceptical of unproven technology. There is a clear need to move beyond simplistic SP-driven projections. In particular, researchers and planners require methods that can incorporate more realistic behavioural responses and adapt as empirical data on these services (gradually) becomes available. To synthesise methodological insights from existing research, Table 1 compares the main characteristics of RP, SP, and hybrid approaches.

Table 1: Comparison of RP, SP, and hybrid approaches in UAM and CCAM demand modelling

Aspect	Revealed Preference (RP)	Stated Preference (SP)	Hybrid (RP–SP combined)
Definition	Uses <i>observed</i> real-world choices to estimate behavioural parameters.	Uses <i>hypothetical</i> scenarios where respondents state their preferred choices among new or modified modes.	Integrates RP and SP to combine realism of observed data with flexibility of hypothetical scenarios.
Data source	Travel survey or operational data for current modes (car, taxi, train, bus).	Choice experiments describing new or future modes (UAM, CCAM).	Joint estimation using both real-world and hypothetical data.
Strengths	High behavioural realism; unbiased by hypothetical bias; parameters transferable.	Captures perception and interest in <i>nonexistent</i> or <i>emerging</i> modes; allows testing of new attributes	Balances realism and innovation; improves calibration of new-mode parameters; cross-validation.
Limitations	Cannot model preferences for new or not-yet-operational modes; limited attribute range.	May suffer from optimism or novelty bias; low external validity; respondents may misjudge service attributes.	Requires complex joint estimation, data harmonisation, and larger sample sizes.
Key model types used	Multinomial Logit, Nested Logit, Mixed Logit using existing revealed data.	SP-based MNL, Mixed Logit, or Latent Class Models.	Joint RP–SP Logit or Hierarchical Bayesian models using scaling factors.

Representative UAM/CCAM studies	Wang & Zhang (2019) [3]. Gurumurthy & Kockelman (2021)[2]	Lv et al. (2024) [4]. Boddupalli et al. (2024) [5]. Brunelli et al. (2023)[6]. Fu et al. (2019) [17]. Jang et al. (2025) [7]. Samadzad et al. (2024) [8]	Coppola et al. (2024) [20]. De Clercq et al. (2022) [21]. Rimjha et al. (2021) [22]
Main behavioural insights	RP data confirms time and cost sensitivities for existing modes, enabling coefficient transfer.	SP data highlights early adopters (affluent, time-sensitive travellers) and bias toward speed and novelty.	Hybrid models enhance predictive validity and allow extrapolation to unobserved technologies.
Use in this study	RP-based calibration on 29,000 Brussels Airport passengers ensures behavioural realism.	Provides benchmark values from literature for hypothetical UAM/CCAM scenarios.	Conceptually adopted via general-coefficient DCM bridging RP calibration and SP-driven scenario.

While SP studies dominate the early UAM and CCAM literature due to the absence of real-world data, hybrid and RP-based models offer more robust behavioural transferability. The present study follows this direction by employing an RP-calibrated discrete choice model with general coefficients, thereby combining the realism of observed behaviour with the flexibility required to forecast new modes. This approach enables robust scenario-based demand forecasting by simulating how travellers make trade-offs among mode attributes, such as travel time, cost, convenience, and privacy, even for new and hypothetical options. By relying on shared behavioural assumptions across transport modes, the model allows for the integration of future options alongside current ones. This approach supports flexible, scenario-based demand forecasting, even in contexts where real-world data for new modes is scarce. The study of De Clercq et al supports the assumption that passengers respond similarly to modal attributes and shows how general coefficients can be used to forecast the adoption of new transport modes like CCAM or UAM [21] . Also, the study by Rimjha et al. [22] focuses on estimating commuter demand and assessing the operational feasibility of UAM in Northern California, specifically centered on San Francisco. The authors calibrated a robust mixed conditional logit mode-choice model using existing travel behaviour data from the National Household Travel Survey (NHTS) for conventional modes like driving and public transit. Critically, the model relies on generic variables such as in-vehicle travel time (IVTT) and monetary cost. This approach allowed the coefficients for these core attributes of UAM to be derived from observed commuter choices for existing modes. This methodology demonstrates a pragmatic approach to estimating demand for novel transportation modes by leveraging observable preferences for comparable attributes across established alternatives.

Using this framework, the model can simulate travellers’ responses to various deployment scenarios. By inputting plausible estimates of service attributes, such as UAM prices, CCAM wait times, or vehicle availability, the DCM generates realistic forecasts of mode share that are not solely dependent on stated intentions. Moreover, the model can incorporate heterogeneity in the population, such as varying levels of technology acceptance or value of time, making the predictions more nuanced and policy-relevant. Importantly, this modelling approach is dynamic and adaptable. As new services are piloted and RP data becomes available, the model can be refined to improve its predictive accuracy. Such a tool would enable airport planners and policymakers to assess the viability of deploying UAM and CCAM services, identify high-potential market segments, and design effective supporting measures, such as pricing incentives or marketing strategies, to enhance adoption. Building on these insights, our study applies this modelling framework to Brussels Airport. By calibrating a nested logit model on revealed passenger behaviour and extending it with operational assumptions for CCAM and UAM, we generate demand forecasts that are flexible, scenario-based, and adaptable to future real-world data.

In summary, this study addresses the limitations of SP-based demand forecasts by applying a discrete choice modelling framework, calibrated on revealed passenger behaviour, to a synthetic population of Brussels Airport users. This approach enables transferable and behaviourally grounded forecasts of UAM and CCAM adoption, supporting policymakers and airport planners with evidence-based insights into likely modal shares and adoption patterns.

3. Case Study: Brussels Airport

Brussels Airport (IATA: BRU, ICAO: EBBR), located approximately 11 kilometres northeast of Brussels' city centre in the municipality of Zaventem, serves as Belgium's primary international gateway and is among Europe's most significant aviation hubs. In 2024, the airport welcomed 23.6 million passengers offering direct connections to 210 destinations worldwide through operations by 80 airlines, including Brussels Airlines, TUI fly Belgium, and various international carriers.

Figure 1. Brussels Airport

Figure 2. Modal split for airport access (Brussel Airport Survey Data 2023)

Brussels Airport is well-connected to the city centre and surrounding regions through a variety of transportation options, providing comprehensive passenger transportation and accessibility solutions and ensuring a seamless journey

for travellers. Airport access is well developed with the direct train links, extensive public transport options, easy road access, and inclusive facilities. Based on the survey data, the current distribution of mode choice is shown in Figure 2.

All data used in this study were fully anonymised prior to analysis, and no personal or identifiable information was stored or processed in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

4. Methodology

The methodology used to model airport accessibility using both existing and emerging transport modes, includes the following key steps, Figure 3:

- 1- Generate a synthetic passenger population for Brussels Airport;
- 2- Calibrate a DCM using existing mode data;
- 3- Integrate UAM and CCAM using operational assumptions;
- 4- Apply the updated model to the synthetic population to estimate future demand.

Figure 3: Overall methodology

First, we estimated a synthetic population for Brussels airport passengers using available open-source data and Brussels airport survey data. After that, we used the Brussels airport survey data to estimate a logit discrete choice model for current transportation modes to Brussels airport. Then, using assumptions about the operation of CCAM and UAM, we estimated the travel time and cost for these new transport modes. Finally, we applied the estimated discrete choice model by adding these new transport modes to the synthetic population, allowing us to estimate the demand for each of the future transportation modes. The following sections provide detailed explanations of each of these steps.

4.1. Synthetic Population

The goal of this component is to generate a synthetic population of travellers for a selected territory. This population should represent individual passengers travelling to or from the airport of study and include key socio-demographic attributes along with trip-related information (such as the number of accompanying persons or the booking class). It should also include the spatial coordinates of the trip's origin and destination, the expected departure time and the desired arrival time at the airport. This detailed demand dataset is then used to estimate the most likely transport mode that a person with those characteristics would choose to reach the airport.

The synthetic population approach is structured as a consistent pipeline as shown in Figure 4. The process starts by reading and transforming raw input data that could be obtained either from open and public data sources or proprietary providers like the airports involved in a study. The goal is bringing all ingested data into a standardized format so that new implementations of the pipeline for other use cases just need to update the first data transformation steps of the pipeline. Then, the pipeline applies a data fusion approach (Iterative Proportional Fitting) to create an aggregated synthetic population [23]. Such a data set indicates the number of persons with a certain combination of attributes (home municipality, age, sex) within the population of a territory, based on marginal information such as the overall age distribution. Furthermore, given intelligently structured marginal input data as described below, it is possible to generate the number of daily airport passengers in each category. The passenger counts for each municipality and socio-demographic group are then used to generate a disaggregated population in which each traveller is represented by one data point in the passenger data set, including their individual information on the home municipality and sociodemographic attributes.

As the next step, the synthetic passenger data set is spatialized making use of public data on the buildings inside the municipalities. This way, it is made sure that every traveller has a specific origin/destination location for the airport trip, which is actually located at a location where a trip could actually take place (excluding, for instance, forests, lakes, or similar). For each individual spatialized traveller, a data enrichment process is then applied by the pipeline. In that process, additional attributes are attached to each traveller such as the number of co-travellers in the group or the booking class. Furthermore, a departure time is added to each individual trip. Altogether, the pipeline produces a synthetic demand data set with individual travellers that have a starting and ending location (one of them in the airport), a planned trip departure time, socio-demographic attributes, and additional trip-based information.

Publicly available data published by the Belgian statistical office STATBEL have been used to characterise Brussels Airport catchment area. These data are available at two geographic levels: municipalities and statistical sectors. The municipal-level data provide information on the sociodemographic structure of the population [24], while the statistical sector data offer more

granular spatial detail within each municipality [25], as statistical sectors are defined as subdivisions of municipalities, with each sector belonging to exactly one municipality.

Figure 4: Schema of the passenger synthesis process

Additionally, we make use of a passenger survey conducted by Brussels Airport, in 2023. It contains information on more than 29,000 respondents per year. Note that the 29,000 passengers are only a sample of all airport passengers at BRU, which we assumed to be representative. Accepting this assumption, we can derive the most probable total number of passengers with a certain age and sex by scaling up those values such that we reach the overall average of daily passengers when summing over all individuals. For that purpose, Brussels Airport has provided passenger statistics for 2023. Iterative Proportional Fitting (IPF) is configured to consider multiple marginal constraints: the number of persons per municipality, age group, and sex based on municipality-level census data, as well as the number of persons per statistical sector (19,795 constraints).

In addition, the IPF integrates information from the passenger survey. Specifically, it considers the number of persons identified with a positive “is passenger” attribute, disaggregated by age group and sex. This additional constraint ensures that the synthetic population is consistent with the observed passenger characteristics.

Note that no explicit constraint on the total number of passengers need to be added as this number is established implicitly by enforcing the number of passengers in each municipality / age / sex category. The seed data is structured as a tensor in four dimensions: statistical sector (from which a municipality can be derived implicitly), age, sex, “is passenger” [26]. The IPF algorithm tracks convergence based on the update factors α_{ik} applied to the counts c_i during each iteration. These update factors reflect how much a specific group (or cell in the multidimensional tensor) is scaled in order to meet a marginal constraint.

The convergence is considered reached when both of the following conditions are met:

$$\left|1 - \min_{ik} \alpha_{ik}\right| < \epsilon \quad \text{and} \quad \left|1 - \max_{ik} \alpha_{ik}\right| < \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Where:

- $\alpha_{ik} = c_i^l / \sum_{i' \in I_k} c_{i'}^l$, representing the relative scaling for constraint k in iteration l
- ϵ is the convergence threshold
- The default value used for ϵ is 10^{-2}

The location assignment is then performed. OpenStreetMap data for the whole of Belgium is obtained from Geofabrik and used to sample locations per statistical sector [27]. In the enrichment process, first the group sizes are imputed to the passenger population. Second, the two passenger profiles “economy” and business” are imputed. Third, the departure hours are imputed based on the survey data. Figure 5 show a sample of the generated trips going to and coming from Brussels Airport.

Figure 5: Example of generated trips going to Brussels airport.

The pipeline has been validated by comparing the generated synthetic population with reference data. The validation process involves several steps, including verifying the fit of the generated data with census data, checking that the socio-demographic distribution of the synthetic population aligns with the reference data, and assessing the accuracy of the generated trip locations. Additionally, the stochastic variability of the synthetic population is evaluated by running multiple random seeds and comparing the resulting outputs. The code repository for the synthetic population is located at the following URL on GitHub accessible to the public: <https://github.com/IRT-SystemX/MAIA> [28]. This synthetic population forms the base upon which we will simulate individual mode choices, using a model calibrated on actual survey data, as described next.

4.2. Discrete Choice Model for Existing Modes

For mode choice model for the current mode of transport for accessibility to airport, the logit discrete choice model is used. The standard logit model assumes that the errors of the utility functions are independently and identically distributed (IID) across alternatives. This assumption implies that the

ratio of the choice probabilities of any two alternatives is unaffected by the presence or absence of other alternatives, known as the Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives (IIA) property. While this property simplifies the estimation process, it can be unrealistic in many real-world scenarios where some choices are more similar to each other than to others. The IIA property can be problematic in scenarios where alternatives share unobserved characteristics, leading to correlated error terms. For example, in the context of airport access, private cars and taxis might share more similarities with each other (e.g., comfort, privacy) than with public transport modes like buses and trains. Also, factors such as weather conditions or traffic congestion might affect the attractiveness of similar modes in a correlated way. When such correlations exist, the standard logit model may produce biased and inconsistent estimates because it does not account for the similarity between alternatives. The nested logit model overcomes these limitations by allowing for correlation within groups of similar alternatives. It does this by grouping alternatives into "nests" where choices within the same nest share some common unobserved characteristics. The nested logit model explicitly accounts for the correlation in unobserved factors within nests, providing a more realistic representation of choice behaviour. The nested logit model allows for different levels of substitution between modes within the same nest compared to those across different nests. This leads to a more accurate estimation of how introducing new modes (like CCAM or UAM) might [29] affect the overall distribution of choices. The process of fitting the logit discrete choice model is described below.

4.2.1. Data Collection, Preparation, and cleaning

The initial step involves collecting survey data from Brussels Airport for the year 2023. The dataset includes 62,119 records and interviews from passengers at Brussels Airport in 2023, of which 29,662 are from passengers residing in Belgium. For the purpose of fitting the model, only the data from passengers residing in Belgium were used, while transfer passengers were excluded from the analysis. This survey includes anonymous socio-demographic characteristics, flight information, details about travellers' places of residence, and the modes of transportation they used to reach the airport. The survey included the following transport modes: car, car sharing, car rental, taxi, bus, train, hotel shuttle services, organised transportation, bicycle, on foot, and motorcycle. However, for the sake of simplification in this study, only the following categories were considered and the rest have been removed: Car (including private car, car sharing, and car rental), Bus (including public bus, hotel shuttle services, and organised transportation), Taxi (including regular taxi, limousine services, and ride-hailing services), and Train. This comprehensive dataset is crucial for calibrating the mode choice model. The data must be prepared by cleaning inconsistencies, missing values, and outliers, ensuring standardized formats suitable for analysis. Relevant explanatory variables expected to influence travellers' mode choices, such as travel time, cost, number of travellers, purpose of travel, and travel conditions, are then selected. 80% of the data was used for training the model, and the remaining 20% was used for testing. After data cleaning, the training data sets includes 21462 records, while the testing data sets includes 5365 records.

4.2.2. Data Enrichment

The cleaned dataset was then enriched by incorporating additional necessary variables for the logit model. Travel time data was obtained using Google Map's distance matrix API and validated with Traffic Scout software [30]. Specifically, the travel time from each postal code in Belgium to Brussels Airport was extracted from Google Map's distance matrix API, and this information was used to enrich the original dataset. Additionally, the travel cost for each mode of transport was calculated and added to the dataset, further enhancing it with detailed cost information. Trip cost for car has been estimated by considering the fuel cost and parking cost. In practice, the distance to the airport has been multiplied by a specific fuel consumption per km (litre per km), and by a fuel cost per litre (€ per litre),

considering only fossil fuel cars. The parking cost was estimated using rates obtained from the official Brussels Airport parking website. Different pricing structures were applied for leisure and business trips, reflecting the assumption that business trips are generally shorter in duration compared to leisure trips. For the taxi cost, a simple regression model has been constructed based on the price that taxi companies and the platform Uber generally ask to make a trip, based on the trip distance. The estimated model is based on 25 requests from various locations in Belgium to Brussels Airport. The resulting linear model gives a very good estimate of the requested price. For the public transportation cost, the price has been estimated, considering a single adult passenger. For the train, a similar regression model has been developed giving for a specified trip distance the ticket price. This model also includes a minimum price (which corresponds to the special airport tax called Diabolo special supplement) and a maximum cap price, which is applicable in Belgium. Finally, the price for the bus ticket has been fixed to 2.3€ for all passengers coming from the two closest regions, namely the province of Flemish-Brabant and the Brussels Capital Region. For passengers coming from beyond those regions, price is estimated to 10€. It should be noted that the model uses normalised values for travel time and travel cost across all transport modes. Normalising the data ensures that variables with different units and scales can be directly compared and appropriately weighted within the model. This approach enhances the model's stability and interpretability, preventing any single variable from disproportionately influencing the results due to its scale. Table 2, present the definition of the variables that have been used in the model.

Table 2: Definition of variables

Variable Name	Definition
Transport mode	
<i>Bus</i>	Indicates that the passenger used bus
<i>Train</i>	Indicates that the passenger used train
<i>Car</i>	Indicates that the passenger used car
<i>Taxi</i>	Indicates that the passenger used taxi
Socio-demographic characteristic	
Age group: The age of the passenger	
<i>Age group 15–17</i>	Passenger is between 15 and 17 years old
<i>Age group 18–24</i>	Passenger is between 18 and 24 years old
<i>Age group 25–34</i>	Passenger is between 25 and 34 years old
<i>Age group 35–44</i>	Passenger is between 35 and 44 years old
<i>Age group 45–54</i>	Passenger is between 45 and 54 years old
<i>Age group 55–64</i>	Passenger is between 55 and 64 years old
<i>Age group 65–74</i>	Passenger is between 65 and 74 years old
<i>Age group 75</i>	Passenger is 75 years old or older
Travel characteristics	
Party size: The number of individuals in the respondent's travel party	
<i>Party-size-1</i>	One passenger travelling alone
<i>Party-size-2</i>	Two passengers travelling together
<i>Party-size-3+</i>	Three or more passengers in the travel group
Cabin class: The travel class selected by the respondent for their flight	
<i>Business class</i>	Passenger is travelling in business class
<i>Economy class</i>	Passenger is travelling in economy class
Mode characteristic	
Travel time: Travel time required to reach Brussels Airport from the respondent's residence using a specific transport mode, extracted from Google Maps	
<i>Bus time</i>	Travel time by bus
<i>Train time</i>	Travel time by train
<i>Car time</i>	Travel time by private car
<i>Taxi time</i>	Travel time by taxi
Travel cost: Monetary cost (€) incurred by a single adult passenger for travelling from their residence to Brussels Airport using a specific transport mode	
<i>Bus cost</i>	Cost of bus travel

<i>Train cost</i>	Cost of train travel
<i>Car cost</i>	Cost of car travel including estimated fuel and parking fees
<i>Taxi cost</i>	Cost of taxi travel based on a linear model derived from real price observations

4.2.3. Model Estimation and Calibration

In order to calibrate the mode choice model, several model structures for the utility function were explored and tested. This included testing whether variables should be included as continuous or categorical and experimenting with different combinations of independent variables. Model fitting involved using the training data to estimate the parameters. Multiple iterations and settings were tested to achieve the best-performing model. More than 200 different model configurations were tested to find the optimal fit. Initially, over 15 independent variables were considered. To determine whether each independent variable has a relationship with mode choice, the distribution of each variable by mode choice was analysed. These distributions were examined for all independent variables. The final model included variables selected based on their statistical significance and contribution to improving the model's predictive accuracy. Python Biogeme package was used to estimate the parameters of the utility functions by maximizing the likelihood function that expresses the probability of observing the given choices in the survey data.

4.2.4. Model Testing and Validation

The developed model was rigorously tested using the test dataset. The model's performance was evaluated through metrics such as predictive accuracy, a confusion matrix, and statistical measures like log-likelihood and McFadden's R-squared.

Figure 6: Nested discrete choice model

The best-fitted model for the current modes of transport (Bus, Train, Car, Taxi) is a nested logit discrete choice model, as depicted in Figure 6. The utility functions for each mode were defined as follows:

$$U_{Bus} = ASC_{Bus} + B_{Time_Public} \cdot BusTime + B_{Cost_Public} \cdot BusCost + B_{Age_public} \cdot Age_{group_{1834}} + B_{CO_Public} \cdot Party_{size_3} + B_{Class_Public} \cdot BusinessClass \quad (2)$$

$$U_{Train} = ASC_{train} + B_{Time_Public} \cdot TrainTime + B_{Cost_Public} \cdot TrainCost + B_{Age_public} \cdot Age_{group_{1834}} + B_{CO_Public} \cdot Party_{size_3} + B_{Class_Public} \cdot BusinessClass \quad (3)$$

$$U_{car} = ASC_{Car} + B_{Time_Private} \cdot CarTime + B_{Cost_Private} \cdot CarCost + B_{Age_private} \cdot Age_{group_{1834}} + B_{CO_Private} \cdot (Party_{size_1} + Party_{size_2}) + B_{Class_Private} \cdot BusinessClass \quad (4)$$

$$U_{Taxi} = ASC_{Taxi} + B_{Time_Private} \cdot TaxiTime + B_{Cost_Private} \cdot TaxiCost + B_{Age_private} \cdot Age_{group_{1834}} \\ + B_{Co_Private} \cdot (Party_{size_1} + Party_{size_2}) + B_{Class_private} \cdot BusinessClass \quad (5)$$

The equations represent the utility functions for different modes of transportation (Car, Train, Taxi, Bus), capturing the preferences and choices of individuals based on various factors. Each mode has an alternative-specific constant (ASC_{Car} , ASC_{train} , ASC_{Taxi} , ASC_{Bus}) to account for inherent preferences not explained by other variables. The coefficients $B_{Time_Private}$ and B_{Time_Public} measure the impact of travel time for private (Car, Taxi) and public (Train, Bus) transportation, respectively. Costs associated with private vehicle travel (CarCost, TaxiCost) and public modes are accounted for by $B_{Cost_Private}$, and B_{Cost_Public} , respectively. The coefficients $B_{Age_Private}$ and B_{Age_Public} represent the effect of age on preferences for private and public transportation. The influence of the number of travel company on private ($B_{Co_Private}$) and public (B_{Co_Public}) transportation choices is also included. Additionally, $B_{Class_Private}$ and B_{Class_Public} capture the effect of cabin class on preferences for private and public transportation.

To allow for integration of hypothetical modes (UAM, CCAM), we adopted a general coefficient approach within each nest. The model assumes that passengers respond similarly to the attributes of different transport modes. This assumption justifies the use of general coefficients (shared across alternatives within each nest of the model) for the relevant attributes. This means the same parameters (e.g., $B_{Time_Private}$, $B_{Cost_Private}$) apply to all private modes, and likewise for public modes. This structure supports transferability by enabling the estimation of utility for modes that are behaviourally similar but not yet observed. The use of general coefficients improves model stability, prevents overfitting, and simplifies the integration of new alternatives. This modelling choice is central to extending the framework beyond currently operational transport services.

4.4. Extension to UAM and CCAM

When modelling airport ground-access mode choice, a common nesting logic is to separate private/on-demand modes (like private cars, taxis, ride-hailing) from public transport modes (buses, rail, etc.), reflecting correlation in unobserved factors within each category. This structure accounts for the fact that, for example, driving one's own car or taking a taxi share convenience and privacy features that distinguish them from public transit. Recent research suggests that emerging modes such as CCAM services and UAM services exhibit behavioural similarities to these traditional private modes, justifying their placement in the same nest as cars and taxis in a nested logit framework. The literature supports grouping CCAM and UAM alternatives in the same nest as cars and taxis due to their shared characteristics: on-demand availability, point-to-point service, small vehicle capacity, and appeal to time-sensitive travellers. Gurumurthy & Kockelman simulated the impact of SAVs on Austin airport access, finding that SAVs can significantly replace private car and taxi trips, reducing overall ground vehicle use (~30% drop) [2]. This substitution effect supports treating SAVs as part of the same behavioural category as cars/taxis in choice models. Jang et al. concluded that UAM appeals to travellers who value time and frequently use taxis, effectively calling it "a taxi in the sky" [7]. This justifies nesting UAM with taxi/private car, since these modes share customer preferences and use-cases. Also, Chen et al. used a random-coefficient logit (BLP) model for UAM mode share in China, with a nested logit as a benchmark for mode grouping [31]. They observed that allowing more elasticity between UAM and private modes produced realistic sharing rates, reinforcing that UAM competes closest with private auto travel. Therefore, in this study, we assumed that CCAM and UAM exhibit similar behavioural patterns to car and taxi and therefore assigned them to the car and taxi (private transport) nest. Based on this assumption, the updated model used for application to the synthetic population is structured as follows. The utility functions for the newly introduced modes are also shown here.

Figure 7: Nested discrete choice model for new modes of transport

$$U_{UAM} = ASC_{UAM} + B_{Time_Private} \cdot UAMTime + B_{Cost_Private} \cdot UAMCost + B_{Age_Private} \cdot Age_{group1834} + B_{Co_Private} \cdot (Party_{size_1} + Party_{size_2}) + B_{Class_Private} \cdot BusinessClass \quad (6)$$

$$U_{CCAM} = ASC_{CCAM} + B_{Time_Private} \cdot CCAMTime + B_{Cost_Private} \cdot CCAMCost + B_{Age_Private} \cdot Age_{group1834} + B_{Co_Private} \cdot (Party_{size_1} + Party_{size_2}) + B_{Class_Private} \cdot BusinessClass \quad (7)$$

Once the discrete choice model is calibrated, we extend it to include CCAM and UAM using well-defined operational assumptions, detailed in the following section.

4.5. CCAM and UAM Operations

In order to apply the discrete choice model to the synthetic population, it was necessary to estimate several parameters: the alternative specific constants (ASC) for UAM and CCAM, as well as their respective travel time and travel cost variables. In the absence of RP data for UAM and CCAM, the ASCs for these modes were approximated as the average of the empirically estimated ASCs for car and taxi. This choice reflects the behavioural similarity of UAM and CCAM to conventional private and on-demand transport services, with which they share attributes such as flexibility, privacy, and direct access. The averaging approach is consistent with the nesting structure of the model, aligns with the general-coefficient specification adopted across private modes, and avoids introducing bias from assuming zero or arbitrary ASC values. While preliminary, this method provides a behaviourally grounded proxy that can be refined as usage data becomes available. Also, the travel time and cost components for UAM and CCAM were then calculated using the assumptions in Table 3 [32].

Table 3: Assumptions of UAM and CCAM

Mode	Attribute	Description	Formula / Assumption
UAM	In-vehicle travel time	Travel time inside eVTOL, based on aerial distance	t_e is calculated based on the assumed eVTOL cruise speed of 120km/h
	Out-of-vehicle time	Additional time for access, waiting, and boarding	$t_a = 10$ minutes
	Access time to vertiport	Car travel time from residence to nearest vertiport	$t_d =$ car travel time from origin to vertiport
	Total UAM travel time	Sum of all components	$UAM\ Time = t_e + t_a + t_d$
	Travel cost	Fixed fare per passenger-kilometre	€5 per km
CCAM	Travel time (business class)	Equivalent to private car travel time	CCAM time = car travel time
	Travel cost (business class)	Equivalent to traditional taxi fare	CCAM cost = taxi fare
	Travel time (economy class)	1.5 times car travel time	CCAM time = 1.5 × car travel time
	Travel cost (economy class)	50% of traditional taxi fare	CCAM cost = 0.5 × taxi fare

The assumed €5 per kilometre fare for UAM reflects the mid-range cost estimates reported in multiple techno-economic assessments of early eVTOL services. According to Hader et al. (2024) and Roland Berger & DLR (2024) [32], initial commercial operations are expected to charge between €4 and €6 per passenger-kilometre, depending on vehicle configuration, utilisation rate, and vertiport costs. Comparable benchmarks are also reported by Rimjha et al. (2021) [22] for Dallas–Fort Worth and by Boddupalli et al. (2024) [5] for US metropolitan areas, both adopting fares around \$4–5 per mile (\approx €4–5/km) for baseline scenarios. Hence, the €5/km assumption represents a conservative central estimate for near-term premium airport shuttle operations.

For CCAM, the 1.5× detour multiplier for shared (economy) services is consistent with simulation studies of shared autonomous vehicles (SAVs). Gurumurthy and Kockelman (2021) [2] observed average detours between 20–40% in airport access operations, while Chouaki et al. (2025) [33] report similar operational ranges (1.3×–1.7× of direct car time). Thus, the selected value of 1.5× reflects a realistic midpoint between modest and heavy pooling scenarios, capturing typical delays from passenger pick-ups and dynamic routing.

A crucial operational element in implementing UAM services is selecting suitable locations for vertiports across urban areas. To tackle it, a demand-based approach was adopted, aiming to identify zones where potential demand for a future UAM airport shuttle service would be maximised [9]. The process began by estimating potential UAM demand, assuming one vertiport per postal code. The aim was to identify areas with the highest latent demand, purely from a demand perspective. Postal codes beyond 50 km from Brussels Airport were excluded due to eVTOL range limits. Those within 5 km were also removed to prevent clustering too close to the airport, where other transport options remain viable. Using this setup, the discrete choice model was applied to simulate UAM demand. The model estimated how many trips might originate from each postal code, taking into account users' willingness to adopt UAM, cost sensitivity, and ease of access to the airport. To evaluate each area's potential, a composite demand indicator was calculated for each postal code. This indicator combined the average probability of residents within a 5 km radius choosing UAM with the total population of the postal code, capturing both the intensity and reach of interest in the service. Next, spatial constraints were applied to refine the results. Additionally, if two high-demand postal codes were within 3 km of each other, only the one with the higher demand was retained to avoid redundancy.

Figure 8: Vertiport locations in Belgium

After this filtering, five urban locations (three in Brussels, one in Leuven and one in Mechelen) were selected as vertiport sites (Figure 8). These represent the most demand-efficient choices for deploying UAM services in Belgium.

It is assumed that CCAM setup in the MAIA framework is operationalised through on-demand SAVs, functioning similarly to taxi services but differentiated by booking class. CCAMs are dispatched from predefined stations located near airports or urban nodes and operate within a maximum service radius (e.g., 50 km). They follow configurable constraints such as minimum wait times and maximum detour limits (typically 15–30 minutes). These services are class-based: economy-class travellers benefit from a lower fare than conventional taxis, but experience longer travel times due to the shared nature of the ride and the possibility of detours to collect other passengers. In contrast, business-class travellers receive exclusive rides with no detours, achieving travel times comparable to taxis but at the same cost as a standard taxi fare. The booking system handles prioritisation, influencing routing, queuing, and vehicle allocation, while real-time rebalancing strategies are applied to optimise fleet distribution and service efficiency. For more detailed insights on the configuration and functioning of these services, readers are encouraged to refer to the paper by Chouak et. al. [33].

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Discrete choice model results

The estimation results of the discrete choice model calibrated using the Brussels Airport passenger survey are summarized below. All variables in the model are statistically significant, indicating a robust and reliable model (Table 4 and Figure 9). As can be seen the McFadden’s R-Squared is equal to 0.404, which represent the good fit of the model.

Table 4: Mode choice model parameter estimation

Name	Value	Robust Std Err	Robust t-test	Robust p-value
<i>ASC_{Bus}</i>	-1.21	0.124	-9.74	0
<i>ASC_{Car}</i>	3.33	0.0554	60.2	0
<i>ASC_{Taxi}</i>	-1.51	0.0424	-35.7	0
<i>B_{Time Public}</i>	-0.0155	0.000845	-18.3	0
<i>B_{Cost Public}</i>	-0.0666	0.0062	-10.8	0
<i>B_{Age Public}</i>	0.357	0.0184	19.4	0
<i>B_{Co Public}</i>	-1.03	0.0602	-17.1	0
<i>B_{Class Public}</i>	-0.229	0.0415	-5.52	3.37e-08
<i>B_{Time Private}</i>	-0.0187	0.00189	-9.92	0
<i>B_{Cost Private}</i>	-0.0597	0.000998	-59.8	0
<i>B_{Age Private}</i>	-0.147	0.0184	-7.97	1.55e-15
<i>B_{Co Private}</i>	0.912	0.0408	22.3	0
<i>B_{Class Private}</i>	0.139	0.0415	3.35	0.000797
μ_{public}	0.912	0.0696	12.9	0
$\mu_{private}$	0.747	0.018	41.6	0

Number of Estimated Parameters=15
Sample Size=21,462
Null Log Likelihood=-29,090
Final Log Likelihood=-17,349.39
McFadden’s R-Squared=0.404
Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)= 34,728.62
Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC)= 34,847.89

The ASCs capture the intrinsic preference for each mode of transport, independent of the observed variables. The ASC for car is highly positive (+3.33), suggesting that, all else being equal, passengers

have a strong inherent preference for travelling by car. In contrast, the ASCs for taxi (−1.51) and bus (−1.21) are negative, indicating that these modes are less preferred compared to the base alternative (train). Travel time has a negative impact on utility for both public and private modes, confirming that longer travel durations reduce the likelihood of choosing a given mode. The coefficient for public travel time (−0.0155) shows that passengers are sensitive to the time it takes to reach the airport by bus or train. The coefficient for private travel time (−0.0187) is even more negative, indicating that passengers are slightly more time-sensitive when using car or taxi. This suggests that time efficiency is a particularly important factor for private transport users. Cost also plays a significant role in mode choice. The coefficients for public transport cost (−0.0666) and private transport cost (−0.0597) are both negative, showing that as travel costs increase, the likelihood of choosing that mode decreases. The impact of cost is slightly higher for public transport, implying that public transport users are somewhat more cost-sensitive. This could reflect tighter budget constraints among typical public transport users. Age appears to influence mode preferences significantly. The coefficient for age group 18–34 is positive for public transport (+0.357) and negative for private transport (−0.147). This suggests that younger travellers are more inclined to use public transport options like train and bus, while older travellers tend to prefer the comfort and convenience of private modes such as car and taxi. Group size has very strong effect. Smaller group sizes (one or two people) increase the utility of private transport (+0.912), as cars and taxis are more practical and cost-effective for such group sizes. The presence of three or more travellers in a group significantly reduces the likelihood of choosing public transport (−1.03), likely due to the inconvenience of coordinating group travel or carrying shared luggage. Passengers flying in business class are more likely to choose private transport modes. The coefficient for business class is negative for public transport (−0.229) and positive for private transport (+0.139). This indicates that business class travellers prefer the comfort, flexibility, and convenience associated with car and taxi travel, and are less inclined to use public transport. The estimated μ values for the public and private nests are both within the valid range ($0 < \mu < 1$), confirming the appropriateness of the nested logit model. The μ value for public transport is 0.912, suggesting moderate correlation between bus and train alternatives. The μ value for private transport is 0.747, indicating a stronger correlation between car and taxi choices. These values imply that unobserved factors affecting the choice between car and taxi are more similar than those between bus and train, justifying the model’s nesting structure.

Figure 9: Confusion Matrix Heatmap

The results clearly indicate that travel by car is the most preferred mode for accessing Brussels Airport, even after controlling for travel time, cost, socio-demographics, and trip characteristics. Time and cost are important deterrents across all modes, while younger age, smaller group size, and economy class increase the likelihood of using public transport. In contrast, business travellers, older passengers, and larger groups (e.g., two to four travellers) are more likely to choose private modes. The nested logit structure effectively captures the similarities within each nest, providing a nuanced understanding of traveller preferences and behaviour. Building on the calibrated model, we apply it to a synthetic population representing airport passengers across Belgium. This allows us to simulate mode choice behaviour for both current transport options and future services (CCAM and UAM) under realistic operational assumptions. The results below show how introducing these new modes affects demand distribution and reveals key patterns of modal shift and user segmentation.

By comparing Figure 10 and Figure 2 we can say that the private car remains the most commonly used mode; only, its share drops from 54.2% in current situation to 49.7% when UAM and CCAM are introduced. This decline indicates that part of the car demand is absorbed by these new alternatives. Train usage remains stable at around 25%, while taxi and bus use declines slightly in the presence of more advanced transport options, suggesting early signs of modal shift among airport travellers.

Figure 10: Distribution of airport passengers' mode choice due to introduction of UAM & CCAM (model)

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Figure 11: Modal shift to UAM: Share of UAM users by previous mode

Figure 12: Modal shift to CCAM: Share of CCAM users by previous mode

In Figure 11 and Figure 12, the value of the share of UAM and CCAM users by previous mode is presented. The share of UAM and CCAM users by previous mode quantifies the proportion of users who chose a new mobility option (either UAM or CCAM) in the scenario with new modes, based on their previously selected transport mode in the current situation.

These variable expresses, as a percentage, the origin mode distribution of new mobility adopters, allowing us to identify which traditional modes contribute most to the uptake of UAM and CCAM. This variable is crucial for understanding behavioural shifts and the substitution patterns toward innovative modes. By normalising the results to the total number of UAM or CCAM users, the analysis corrects for imbalances in the size of the original user groups (e.g., more car users in general), offering a fair comparison across all traditional modes. Figure 11 shows that the vast majority of UAM users (73%) come from taxi, making taxi the primary source of UAM adoption. This highlights that UAM is primarily attracting users who previously relied on flexible, on-demand transport services. In addition, 14% of UAM users previously used car, followed by 10% from train and just 3% from bus. These proportions suggest that UAM is being perceived as a premium, time-saving, or status-enhancing option, drawing most strongly from modes associated with comfort and convenience. Figure 12 shows that most of the CCAM users come from the car, representing 67% of CCAM adopters. This indicates that CCAM is primarily replacing personal car use, appealing strongly to users already relying on individualised, private mobility. The second most significant group comes from taxi, with 20% of CCAM users previously being taxi users, followed by 11% from bus and only 2% from train. This pattern reinforces the notion that CCAM is a compelling alternative for those who favour flexibility and independence in their travel behaviour.

5.2. Spatial analysis

Beyond aggregate modal shifts, spatial analysis offers additional insight into how preferences vary geographically; therefore, the following illustrations have been created. These figures display the probability that each synthetic passenger travelling to Brussels Airport will choose a specific mode of transport. In these visualisations, each point represents an individual passenger, and the colour of the point indicates the likelihood of choosing a given mode. The redder the point, the higher the probability of that mode being selected by the passenger. Each colour corresponds to a specific probability range. This means that even if some modes have higher probabilities, they may still appear in the same colour if they fall within the same range.

Figure 13 show that bus usage is highly concentrated in the cities of Leuven and Brussels. As these cities have good bus connection, making the bus a convenient and cost-effective option. It also reflects a potential preference among passengers in these areas for more affordable transport, or it may signal effective public transport policies promoting airport accessibility by bus.

Figure 13: Spatial Distribution of Bus Mode Choice Probabilities to Brussels Airport

The probability of choosing the train mode is relatively high across major Belgian cities, including Antwerp, Liège, Ghent, and Hasselt in addition to Brussels (Figure 14). This broader spatial distribution indicates the widespread availability and perceived reliability of rail services for airport access. It may also reflect the speed and comfort advantages of trains for medium to long-distance trips within the country, positioning it as a competitive alternative to car.

Figure 14: Spatial Distribution of Train Mode Choice Probabilities to Brussels Airport

The demand for private cars is evenly distributed across Belgium, which likely reflects the convenience, flexibility, and door-to-door nature of this mode (Figure 15). It could also imply limited public transport coverage in rural or less connected areas, encouraging people to rely on their own vehicles. Moreover, passengers travelling in groups or carrying luggage may find the car a more practical solution, especially when parking availability at the airport is not a constraint.

Figure 15: Spatial Distribution of Car Mode Choice Probabilities to Brussels Airport

Taxi usage appears to be more localised, with most users located within moderate distances from the airport (Figure 16). This is expected, as taxis become cost-prohibitive for longer journeys. The demand pattern suggests that taxi services are primarily used for short, direct connections where convenience outweighs cost. This mode may also serve travellers with time-sensitive schedules or those unwilling to use shared or public options.

Figure 16: Spatial Distribution of Taxi Mode Choice Probabilities to Brussels Airport

UAM demand appears the most prominent among passengers living within a 10-kilometre radius of Brussels Airport (Figure 17), for the assumed price of 5EUR per km. This indicates that UAM is currently a viable option primarily for short-distance travellers, who slightly benefit from improved travel times for reasonable costs due to shorter aerial distances. However, it's important to note that this demand is highly sensitive to the location and number of vertiports available. If more vertiports were added further from the airport, the potential catchment area for UAM could expand.

Figure 17: Spatial Distribution of UAM Mode Choice Probabilities to Brussels Airport

The CCAM option shows notable interest among travellers from longer distances (Figure 18). Since its cost is assumed to be half that of a taxi, it presents an affordable and appealing middle ground between high-cost private transport and slower public options. It seems especially useful for those in semi-urban and suburban regions who might lack direct access to traditional modes or prefer a more comfortable and efficient alternative. Its attractiveness for long-distance travellers also suggests the importance of positioning CCAM services as a complementary rather than competing mode with buses and trains.

Figure 18: Spatial Distribution of CCAM Mode Choice Probabilities to Brussels Airport

These results highlight how integrating innovative transport options like UAM and CCAM can shift passenger behaviour and expand accessibility to Brussels Airport. The model not only identifies high-potential user segments but also reveals spatial opportunities for targeted service deployment. As a consequence of our modelling strategy, where we extended the utility functions for UAM and CCAM by assigning them the same time and cost coefficients as the private modes, car and taxi, under a general-coefficient specification, the marginal disutility associated with travel time for UAM and CCAM is lower than that for travel cost. Since our model is calibrated using real-world survey data from passengers currently using traditional modes to access the airport, the lower sensitivity to time and higher sensitivity to cost reflect actual behavioural tendencies of travellers. Given these indications, the next section examines the sensitivity of predicted UAM and CCAM shares to changes in their time and cost attributes. This analysis helps to quantify how variations in these parameters might influence modal shares and adoption patterns.

5.3. Sensitivity analysis

To assess the robustness of our model outputs, we conducted sensitivity experiments by modifying the operational inputs specified in Table 3. For UAM, we adjusted the cruise speed to 100, 110, 120, 130, and 150 km/h, corresponding to approximately -20% to $+20\%$ changes in travel time, and varied the fare per kilometre between €4.00, €4.50, €5.00, €5.50, and €6.00, representing -20% to $+20\%$ changes in travel cost. For CCAM, we applied time multipliers and fare multipliers relative to car/taxi for both business and economy services: business services ranged from $0.8\times$ to $1.2\times$ car travel time and $0.8\times$ to $1.2\times$ taxi cost, while economy services ranged from $1.2\times$ to $1.8\times$ car travel time and $0.4\times$ to $0.6\times$ taxi cost, again corresponding to -20% to $+20\%$ changes in travel time and cost. Model coefficients and nesting structures were held constant; only the relevant operational parameters from

Table 3 were altered. Figure 19 to Figure 22 present the resulting modal shares of UAM and CCAM across the different cost and time variation scenarios.

Figure 19: UAM sensitivity to Cost

Figure 20: UAM sensitivity to Time

The sensitivity analysis results demonstrate that UAM is notably more responsive to cost changes than to time changes. For UAM, a -20% reduction in travel cost increases its modal share from 4.7% to 7.2% (+2.5 percentage points), whereas a -20% reduction in travel time only increases its share to 5.9% (+1.2 percentage points). Conversely, cost increases for UAM lead to sharper declines in share compared to equivalent increases in travel time.

Figure 21: CCAM sensitivity to Cost

Figure 22: CCAM sensitivity to Time

For CCAM, the effects are more dramatic: a –20% reduction in travel cost increases its share from 6.8% to 11.1%, while a –20% reduction in travel time raises it to 12.0%. Both parameters have a strong influence, but the slightly larger increase for the time reduction scenario, consistent with the elasticity values (relative time elasticity –3.6 vs relative cost elasticity –3.2), suggests that CCAM demand is at least as sensitive to time changes as it is to cost. Nevertheless, increases in cost have a disproportionately large negative effect, with a +20% cost rise reducing CCAM’s share to just 2.9%, highlighting that pricing remains a critical factor for maintaining competitiveness, particularly for the economy segment that competes directly with lower-cost modes.

Table 5 summarises scenario-based sensitivities for cost and time. As shown, UAM demand responds more to fare changes than equivalent time changes, while CCAM exhibits strong sensitivity to both parameters.

Table 5: Scenario-based sensitivity of predicted shares

Scenario	Share (%)	Scenario	Share (%)
UAM		CCAM	
Base Case	4.7	Base Case	6.8
UAM cost –20%	7.2	CCAM cost –20%	11.1
UAM cost –10%	5.8	CCAM cost –10%	8.9
UAM cost +10%	3.9	CCAM cost +10%	4.6
UAM cost +20%	3.3	CCAM cost +20%	2.9
UAM time –20%	5.9	CCAM time –20%	12.0
UAM time –10%	5.3	CCAM time –10%	9.3
UAM time +10%	4.2	CCAM time +10%	4.3
UAM time +20%	3.6	CCAM time +20%	2.7

These behavioural tendencies are quantified in the elasticity analysis. The average arc elasticities (Table 6) confirm that UAM exhibits a higher absolute elasticity for cost (–1.9) than for time (–1.2), indicating that demand for this premium, time-saving service is nevertheless more responsive to fare changes than to equivalent percentage changes in travel time. For CCAM, both cost (–3.2) and time (–3.6) elasticities are large in magnitude, suggesting that demand is highly sensitive to both parameters. The slightly larger absolute time elasticity implies that improving

CCAM travel times could have an effect on demand comparable to, or even exceeding, the effect of price adjustments.

The inclusion of elasticity estimates alongside the modal share changes strengthens the robustness assessment. While the figures (Figure 19 to Figure 22) provide a visual representation of share shifts under parameter variation, the elasticity measures allow for more generalisable interpretations, enabling comparison with results from other studies or future scenarios. Together, these findings suggest that for UAM, pricing strategies will be pivotal in shaping adoption, whereas for CCAM, both cost management and travel time improvements are equally critical for attracting users.

Table 6: Average arc elasticity for UAM and CCAM

Mode	Parameter	Average arc elasticity
UAM	cost	-1.9
	time	-1.2
CCAM	cost	-3.2
	time	-3.6

6. Conclusion

As new mobility technologies such as CCAM and UAM advance towards real-world deployment, understanding their potential impacts on airport accessibility becomes increasingly vital. These emerging modes promise to reshape how passengers reach airports by offering faster, more convenient alternatives that can bypass conventional ground-based limitations such as congestion and limited public transport coverage. Consequently, developing models that can accurately forecast demand for these innovations is critical for future-proofing transport planning and infrastructure investment.

While several earlier studies have explored the potential of CCAM and UAM, many have relied heavily on SP data and focused on isolated case studies. These approaches, although valuable, often lack the generalisability and methodological flexibility required to evaluate entirely new transport modes under diverse scenarios. This paper addresses that research gap by proposing and applying a robust methodology capable of estimating mode choice for any transport alternative, including novel services not yet widely operational.

Our approach builds upon a discrete choice model calibrated using a comprehensive survey dataset from Brussels Airport. The key innovation lies in using general coefficients (shared across all alternatives within the nested model) which allows for seamless integration of future transport options like CCAM and UAM. This calibration method, grounded in real passenger behaviour, equips the model to extrapolate responses to new modes based on attribute similarities such as travel time, cost, and travel party size, rather than speculative preference data alone.

First, we generated a detailed synthetic population of airport passengers in Belgium, enabling individual-level simulation. We then developed a discrete choice model based on current transport mode usage using a nested logit structure and survey data. Next, we established operational assumptions for UAM and CCAM services, including their expected travel times and costs. The new transport options were integrated into the calibrated model, which was then applied to the synthetic population to produce demand forecasts.

The analysis indicates clear modal shifts with the introduction of UAM and CCAM. UAM adoption is concentrated among passengers previously using taxi services, suggesting a strong appeal to time-sensitive travellers who prioritise speed and flexibility. Meanwhile, CCAM primarily attracts former car users, offering an automated, comfortable alternative that retains the privacy of private transport.

These patterns not only reflect differentiated user segments but also underscore the necessity of tailoring future transport services to distinct passenger profiles and geographical contexts. Overall, UAM captures an estimated 4.7% of total airport access trips, while CCAM accounts for 6.8%, demonstrating that these emerging modes can play a non-negligible role in future airport access strategies.

This study presents a flexible and forward-looking modelling framework for estimating airport access demand, including for emerging transport modes such as UAM and CCAM. However, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the results are based on assumptions regarding the operational characteristics and user perceptions of UAM and CCAM, as no RP data currently exists for these modes. Parameters such as travel time, cost, and alternative-specific constants were inferred from existing private modes (particularly car and taxi) which may not fully capture the distinctive features or perceived utility of UAM and CCAM services. Due to the absence of SP data specifically designed for these emerging modes, it was not possible to statistically test alternative nesting configurations or determine with confidence whether UAM and CCAM are perceived by travellers as being more similar to existing public transport, private car, or other mode groups. Future research should therefore focus on collecting dedicated SP survey data to capture user perceptions of similarity and substitution patterns between these new modes and existing transport options. Such data would enable the application of formal nesting tests (e.g., inclusive value parameter estimation) and allow the nesting structure to be refined, improving both the behavioural realism and transferability of the model to other regions. Second, while the synthetic population and behavioural model structure enable detailed scenario analysis, the precision of forecasts is inherently constrained by the quality and representativeness of the underlying survey and spatial data. Finally, the model assumes stability in behavioural response patterns, which may evolve as users gain experience with new technologies. Despite these limitations, the modelling framework is designed to be assumption-agnostic and readily updatable. As empirical data from future pilot deployments becomes available, the model can be recalibrated to improve its predictive accuracy and continue supporting robust, policy-relevant planning.

7. References

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